

METHODS OF TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

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Annotation: *The article describes the communicative method of teaching a foreign language. The author proposes and considers various forms of work that increase students' motivation to learn a foreign language.*

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Currently, there are three main methods of teaching a foreign language: direct, comparative and mixed.

I. Direct method. It is called direct because its followers are trying to create immediate direct associations between the subject and the word of the foreign language being studied, bypassing the students' native language. They try to create similar direct associations between the meaning of grammatical categories and their forms in a foreign language without comparing them with the semantics of the grammatical categories of the students' native language. In addition to such didactic principles as activity, visibility, accessibility and strength, this method is based on intuitiveness, immanence, reliance on positive language experience, undifferentiated learning, and consistent learning. Of the varieties of the direct method, the audiolingual method is currently the most widely used. and audiovisual methods.

Learning a foreign language in audiolingual method has educational and practical value. The educational value lies in the fact that, while studying a foreign language, a student joins the culture of the people whose language he is studying, and this is possible if he masters a new system of concepts inherent in this language. To learn a new system of concepts is possible only by mastering the language practically. The ultimate goal of practical language acquisition is the ability to speak, understand listening, read and write in the target language.

With regard to the content of training, it is necessary to give priority to the selection of phonetic material and the selection structures. When selecting structures, one should take into account whether they are intended for reproductive or receptive assimilation. The main principles of selection are their use and frequency, as well as indispensability, i.e. the exclusion of synonymous constructions. There is no need to attach great importance to the composition of the vocabulary, considering, however, that first of all, combat words should be learned. Assimilation of significant words is

entirely connected with the interests of students. For them, different topics and a different set of words are recommended.

Language acquisition is based on a skill that is formed on the basis of imitation and repetition. Students must unconsciously master the structures of the language being studied and its phonetic structure and form sentences by analogy. Since each language has its own system of concepts and structures that are unique and unique in another language, they should be studied immanently, without resorting to comparison with the native language of students. The analysis of structures by the audiolingual method entails only reflections about it that are unnecessary for practical mastery of the language, and comparison with the native language generates errors in the language being studied. In cases where it is difficult for a student to understand a globally perceived pattern, various means of external and internal visualization should come to the rescue - transparencies, cinema and context or situation. The use of visual aids and repeated repetition of the material contribute to the strength of its assimilation. Distinguishing between active and passive language material, one can not make a special difference in its assimilation.

Great importance must be attached to the sequence of studying the material and the formation of skills and abilities. The following sequence is recommended: listening - speaking - reading - writing. Speaking exercises follow immediately after listening to the material. Learning to read and write takes place only on the material that is well learned orally, and therefore is postponed to a later time.

The promotion of oral speech is explained by the fact that language is considered primarily as a means of oral communication, while written speech is an inaccurate image of the sound language, which should be taught only after oral speech has been mastered.

Unlike the audio-lingual method, the audio-visual method attaches great importance to the selection of vocabulary. The dictionary was selected on the basis of a thorough analysis of living English. As a result, a dictionary of 1500 words was compiled, which makes it possible to freely conduct a conversation on everyday topics.

II. Comparative method. The comparative method got its name because the study of a foreign language is supposed to be based on its comparison with the native one.

This method is based on didactic principles, and first of all on the principle of consciousness, which means that, as a rule, all studied linguistic phenomena are explained to students before the skills and abilities to use them are created. However, the rules for the use of grammatical and other phenomena are reported only when there are enough examples to illustrate them. Therefore, in the process of teaching, such cases are also possible when individual grammatical phenomena are first perceived as word forms and only then are generalized into rules.

With the comparative method, grammatical rules are only a means of accelerating the learning process, making it possible to consciously use linguistic analogy. Therefore, firstly, among the grammatical rules, only those that apply to a large number of words

are selected. Secondly, the rules themselves are communicated to students only when the grammatical forms formed with the help of these rules can be used in speech or when reading the text, i.e. when these rules can be illustrated on a sufficient amount of lexical material.

With the comparative method, oral speech plays an important role in teaching a foreign language, but it must develop in parallel in connection with other types of speech activity - reading and writing.

III. Mixed method. The mixed, or combined, method got its name from the fact that it combines to some extent the principles of direct and comparative methods. Depending on which principles prevail, it will be either closer to the direct method or to the comparative method. Of the works on the mixed method, the works of F. Kloss and A. Bohlen are currently the most popular.

F. Kloss bases his method on the following provisions:

1. At the first stage, students should assimilate the language material mainly intuitively and immanently, although in case of difficulties, the native language is not excluded, and for better assimilation of the material, exercises in translation.

2. At the second stage, it is proposed to learn grammatical rules and more often resort to translation - the surest means of revealing the meanings of words. A. Bohlen puts forward the following basic principles of learning: Immanence and comparison, reliance on one-sided language experience, undifferentiated learning, consistent learning. A. Bohlen emphasizes the need to get acquainted with the spirit of the people through a comparative study of the grammar of a foreign language and idioms that reflect their thinking.

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